

Diphthong Jihad

A reanalysis of English long vowels and diphthongs as short vowels plus glides

I posit that the long vowels i: and u: and the diphthongs ɔɪ, əʊ, aɪ, aʊ, eɪ and ɪə are more efficiently described in pedagogical contexts as instances of short vowels plus j or w:

i:	ij
u:	uw
ɔɪ	oj
əʊ	ow
aɪ	aj
aʊ	aw
eɪ	ej
ɪə	ijə

The advantage of this is that there is subsequently no need to teach any distinction between short vowels, certain long vowels and diphthongs when teaching English vowels. Instead, vowel production can be achieved with only eight symbols (i, e, a, o, ə, ʌ, u and :):

æ	a
ɑ:	a:
ɒ	o
ɔ:	o:
ɪ	i
i:	ij
e	e
ə	ə
ʌ	ʌ
ʊ	u
u:	uw
ɔɪ	oj
əʊ	ow
aɪ	aj
aʊ	aw
eɪ	ej
ɪə	ijə

It also explains why, in normal speech, certain phonological combinations apparently “insert” a w sound:

go	over	go over
gəʊ	əʊvə	gəʊwəʊvə
go	over	go over
gow	owvə	gowowvə

It also explains why, in normal speech, certain phonological combinations apparently “insert” a j sound:

l	am	l am
aɪ	æm	aɪjæm
l	am	l am
aj	am	ajam

My idea of representing certain long vowels and diphthongs as instances of short vowels plus consonants came from Arabic. In Arabic, what we might otherwise transcribe as i:, u: and aʊ are actually instances of a short vowel plus a consonant: ij (يِ), uw (وُ) and aw (وَ):

مِسْكِين	سُود	زَوْجِي
miski:n	su:d	zaʊdʒi:
(miskijn)	(suwd)	(zawdʒij)

From there, it was simple enough to apply that same principle when considering certain long vowels and diphthongs in English.

NOTE: It is interesting that both Schulz (2005) and Wightwick and Gaafar (2007) transliterate يِ as “ay” and وَ as “aw”, which is logical given that they also transcribe ا as “a”, ي as “y” and و as “w”. However, they then transliterate يِ as “ī” or “ii” and وَ as “ū” or “uu”. This led me to consider that “iy” and “uw” would have perhaps been more consistent alternatives for يِ and وَ and that it was only the bias in English toward considering vowels as either short, long or diphthongised that led to the arguably Anglocentric “ī”, “ii”, “ū” and “uu”:

كَبِير	وَدُود
kabiir	wadūd
(kabiyr)	(waduwd)

References

Eckehard Schulz, 2005, *A student grammar of Modern Standard Arabic*, Cambridge University Press

Jane Wightwick and Mahmoud Gaafar, 2007, *Arabic verbs and essentials of grammar*, McGraw-Hill Education